

Study on the Impact of GST on Chemical Industries

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Abstract

There was a multiple Indirect Tax System in India that has the problem of the Cascading Effect (Tax on Tax System). Chemical Industries is facing some other problems before & after implementing the GST system in India. This study will help us to examine the Impact of GST along with the benefits & challenges which Chemical Industries is facing after the implementation of GST. This study mainly concentrates on identifying the opportunities, threats & Impact of GST on Chemical Industries.

Keywords: Impact of GST, Chemical Industries.

Introduction

Meaning of Goods & Services Tax (GST)

Clauses 366 (12A) of the constitution bill defines GST as “Goods & Services Tax” means any tax on supply of goods, or services or both except taxes on the supply of the liquor for human consumption. Further, clause 366 (12A) of the constitution bill defines Services means anything other than goods.

Thus it can be said that GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacturers, sale & consumption of goods & services at a national level. The proposed tax will be levied on all transactions involving the supply of goods & services, except those which are kept out of its preview.

Note: The word bill may be interpreted as the constitution (122nd) amendment bill 2014.

It will subsume the following taxes:

- Central excise Duty
- Additional Excise Duty
- Service Tax
- Countervailing Duty (CVD)
- Additional Duty of Customs (ADC)
- Surcharge, Education & Secondary or Higher Secondary cess of now

It will subsume the following taxes:

- VAT/ Sales Tax
- Purchase Tax
- Entertainment Tax
- Luxury Tax
- Lottery Tax
- State Surcharge & cesses leviable on the above as

Types of Goods & Services Tax in India

1. **CGST:** Collected by the Central Government on an intra-state sale. (Eg: Maharashtra)
2. **SGST:** Collected by the State Government on an intra-state sale. (Eg: Within Maharashtra)
3. **IGST:** Collected by the Central Government for inter-state sale. (Eg: Maharashtra to Tamil Nadu)
4. **UGST:** Collected by the Union Territory. (Eg: Andaman and Nicobar Islands)

GST Rates in India at a glance

- Exempted Categories: 0
- Commonly used Goods & Services: 5%
- Standard Goods & Services fall under 1st Slab: 12%
- Standard Goods & Services fall under 2nd Slab: 18%
- Special category of Goods & Services including Luxury Goods: 28%

Chemical Industry

The Chemical industry is one of the oldest industries in India, which contributes significantly towards the industrial and economic growth of the nation. Since this industry has numerous forward and backward linkages, it is called the backbone of the industrial and agricultural development of the country and provides building blocks for many downstream industries.

Impact of GST on Chemical Industry

GST can have a long – term positive impact on the chemical sector. Almost every Predictable impact of GST on the Indian industrial sector looks Positive, especially for the chemicals industry. Chemical Businesses in India have long suffered the wrath of added taxations on their production capacity as well as their Consumption demands.

The existing taxations have impelled the raise in the production costs of manufacturing vital chemicals, which has resulted in the price – hike of the end products and made such goods unaffordable for gross consumption.

Hence the GST bill is trusted to be seminal for the unbarred progress of the Indian Chemical Industry in the years to come.

Review of Literature

Pinki et al. (2014) studied, “Goods and Service Tax Panacea For Indirect Tax System in India” and concluded that the new NDA government in India is positive towards implementation of GST and it is beneficial for central government, state government and as well as for consumers in long run if its implementation is backed by strong IT infrastructure.

Kumar (2014) studied, “Goods and Service Tax - A way forward” and concluded that after implementation of GST in India much indirect tax system will be finished, and there would be only one tax i.e., GST, which is expected to encourage unbiased tax structure.

Sehrawat and Dhanda (2015) studied, “GST in India: A Key Tax Reform,” and concluded that due to dissilient the dissilient environment of the India economy, it is the demand of time to implement GST.

Anushuya and Narwal (2014) studied “Application of CGE Modals In GST” and concluded that both GST & CGE are very popular all over the world, but GST is a powerful concept in the field of indirect taxes.

Chaurasia et al. (2016) Studied, “Role of Goods and Services Tax in the growth of Indian economy” and concluded that in overall GST will be helpful for the development of Indian economy and this will also help in improving the Gross Domestic Products of the country more than two percent.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the Impact of GST on Chemical Industries
- To study the departmental views & perceptions on newly implemented Tax system (GST)
- To come out with the Findings & Suggestions where ever necessary

Scope of Study

This study will help us to know the Impact, Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities &, Threats of the Chemical Industries due to GST implementation in India.

Methodology of Data Collection

Each work to be completed by following steps or methodology continuously & effectively to get the preparation of the project report. To pursue the relevant information initially the objectives of the study are led down under the guidance of the teacher of the structured questionnaire among the departmental heads in the chemical Industries.

Sources of Data Collection

1. Primary Data:

This study will be conducted by collecting the data from the Company Departmental Managers through Questionnaire & informal interview/discussions for the Data Analysis & Interpretation & Findings

2. Secondary Data:

This study will be conducted by the collection of data through secondary sources for Introduction & Industry Profile GST Policy

3. Respondents

This study is been performed by collecting data from the managers & the executives of the organization

Field Study

- Method of a collection of data is through Questionnaire
- The tool used for in collection of data for this research study was through Standard Questionnaire

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Table Showing the Frequency Rate of the Responses in the Chemical Industries

Response Status	Number of Respondents	Total
Respondents	25	25
Non – Respondents	0	0
Total	25	25

Table 2 Table Showing the About how Frequently GST Returns are Filed by the various Chemicals Industries

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Monthly	17	68.00%
Quarterly	2	8.00%
Half Yearly	4	16.00%
Annually	2	8.00%
Total	25	100%

Analysis

The Majority of the respondents,i.e. chemical industries,think that the GST returns are filed mostly on a monthly basis.

Table 3 Table showing the demand for the products by clients after imposing GST

	Number of Responses	Percentage
Yes	12	48.00%
No	1	4.00%
To a certain extent	10	40.00%
Not sure	2	8.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table,we can analyse that 48.00% of respondents are of opinion that there is a rise in the demand for their products, 4.00% of respondents are of opinion that there is a no rise in the demand for their products, 40.00% of respondents are of opinion that there is a rise in the demand for their products to a certain extent and 8.00% of respondents are not sure about their opinion related to the demand for their products.

Chart 3 Chart showing the demand for the products by clients after imposing GST

Interpretation

The majority of the respondents think that there is a rise in the demand for their products by clients after imposing GST.

Table 4 Table Showing the GST Influence on Each Department (Departmental Perspective)

	Purchase Department	Sales & Marketing Department	Finance & Accounts Department	Production Department	HR Department
Yes	0	3	0	4	0
No	2	1	1	0	1
Maybe	8	2	3	0	0
Total	10	6	4	4	1

Analysis: From the above table it is understood that,

Purchase Department

2 out of 10 respondents in this department think that GST has not influenced their department & the other eight respondents are of the opinion that they are not sure whether GST has influenced their department or not.

Sales & Marketing Department

3 out of 6 respondents in this department think that GST has influenced their department, 1 of the respondent think that GST has not influenced their department & the other two respondents think that they are not sure whether GST has influenced their department or not.

Finance & Accounts Department

1 out of 4 respondents in this department think that GST has not influenced their department & the other three respondents think that they are not sure whether GST has influenced their department or not.

Production Department

All the four respondents in this department think that GST has not influenced their department.

HR Department

Respondents in this department think that GST has not influenced their department.

Table 5 Table showing the GST influence on each Department (Company’s Perspective)

	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	7	28.00%
No	5	20.00%
Maybe	13	52.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyse that 28.00% of the respondents think that the GST had influenced on each department, 20.00% of the respondents think that the GST had not influenced on each department & 52.00% of the respondents think that they are not sure whether GST had influenced on each department or not

Chart 5 Chart showing the GST influence on each department

Interpretation

The majority of the respondents think that they are not sure whether GST had influenced each department or not.

Table 6 Table showing the expenditure which is mostly affected by GST

	No. of respondents	Percentage
Raw Materials	6	24.00%
Labour Cost	0	0.00%
Indirect Overheads	12	48.00%
All the Above	7	28.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyse that 24.00% of respondents think that the expenditure on Raw Materials is mostly affected from GST, 48.00% of respondents think that the expenditure on Indirect Overheads is mostly affected from GST & 28.00% of respondents think that the expenditure on Raw materials, Labour cost & Indirect Overheads is mostly affected by GST.

Chart 6 Chart showing the expenditure which is mostly affected by GST

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents think that expenditure on Indirect Overheads is mostly affected by GST

Table 7 Table showing whether the company is affected or not due to GST implementation

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	14	56.00%
No	4	16.00%
Maybe	7	28.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyse that 56.00% of the respondents are of the opinion that the company is affected due to GST implementation, 16.00% of the respondents are of the opinion that the company is not affected due to GST implementation, 28.00% of the respondents are of the opinion that they are not sure whether the company is affected or not affected due to GST implementation

Chart 7 Chart showing whether the company is affected or not due to GST implementation**Interpretation**

Majority of the respondents are of the opinion that the Company is affected due to GST implementation

Table 8 Table showing whether the company support the GST Tax policy or not

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	25	100.00%
No	0	0.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can that the majority of the respondents think that the Chemicals India Pvt Ltd supports the GST Tax policy

Table 9 Table showing, whether the GST act as a boon or bare for the company

	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Advantage	24	96.00%
Disadvantage	1	4.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyse that 96.00% of the respondents think that GST tax policy act as an Advantage for the company and the 4.00% of the respondents think that GST tax policy act as a Disadvantage for the company

Chart 9 Chart shows, whether the GST act as a boon or bare for the company

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents think that GST tax policy act as an Advantage to the company

Table10 Table showing the reason why GST acts an advantage to the company

	Number of Responses	Percentage
GST removes 17 Indirect taxes	3	12.50%
Removal of Cascading Effect	2	8.33%
Reduces tax liability	1	4.17%
Online procedure	0	0.00%
All the above	18	75.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis:

From the above table, we can analyse that 12.50% of the respondents think that GST removes 17 Indirect taxes, 8.33% of the respondents think that GST helps to remove the Cascading Effect, 4.17% of the respondents think that GST reduces the Tax liability & 75.00% of the respondents think that GST removes 17 Indirect taxes, Cascading Effect& reduces the tax liability.

Chart 10 Chart showing the reason why GST acts an advantage to the company

Interpretation: The majority of the respondents agree that the GST tax policy acts as an Advantage to the company.

Table 11 Table showing the reason why GST acts a Disadvantage to the company

	Number of Responses	Percentage
Differential Tax rates & many complexities	1	4.00%
High confusion regarding the product classification	0	0.00%
GST structure increases the business costs	0	0.00%
All the above	0	0.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyse that only 4.00% of the respondents think that GST acts as Disadvantage to the company due to Differential Tax rates for different products & many complexities.

Table 12 Table showing the Impact of GST on chemical industries

	Number of Responses	Percentage
Positive	25	100.00%
Negative	0	00.00%
No impact	0	00.00%
Not sure	0	00.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis: All the respondents think that there is a positive effect of GST on Chemicals Industries

Table 13 Table showing the rating of GST system (5 is the highest & 1 is the lowest)

	Number of Responses	Percentage
5	10	40.00%
4	12	48.00%
3	3	12.00%
2	0	0.00%
1	0	0.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Analysis

From the above table, we can analyse that 40.00% of the respondents had rated the GST system as 5, 48.00% of the respondents had rated the GST system as 4, 12.00% of the respondents had rated the GST system as 3.

Chart 13 Table showing the rating of GST system (5 is the highest & 1 is the lowest)

Interpretation

The majority of the respondents had rated the GST system as four, where 5 is the highest & 1 is the lowest.

Findings

1. Chemical Industries supports the GST Tax policy
2. GST returns are filed mostly on a monthly basis
3. According to the analysis & the data gathered from the companies expenditure on Indirect Overheads is much affected by GST
4. Differential Tax rates for different products & many complexities leads the employees to feel that the GST tax policy is a Burden to the company
5. There is a positive effect of GST on the Chemical Industries
6. Chemical Industries has rated the GST system as 4 & 5 (5 is the highest & 1 is the lowest)
7. GST Tax policy is highly influenced on Purchase Department

Suggestions

All the companies should welcome the GST because it has a positive effect in the long run.

Limitations of the Study

1. This study is only restricted only to the Chemical Industries
2. Respondents were not ready to respond in their busy schedule
3. Duration of the study was not sufficient
4. Due to the time constraints, the research assumptions did & are obtained through questionnaire & informal interview keeping in view that the respondents had given the appropriate information about the company

Conclusion

GST can have a long – term positive impact on the chemical sector. Impact of GST on the Indian industrial sector looks Positive, especially for the chemicals industry. GST Tax policy offers lots of benefits like Input Tax Credit, Reduces the Tax Liability, Removes Cascading Effect, etc. Through all this, we can conclude that the GST has a positive impact on Chemical Sectors.

Bibliography

Books

1. Goods & Services Tax – Laws & Practice
2. B.G. Bhaskara, M.RamachandraGowda, Manjunath.N, Naveen Kumar.I.M

Websites

1. <https://www.quora.com/What-is-GST-What-are-its-implications-on-the-chemical-industry>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWOT_analysis
3. <https://www.paisabazaar.com/tax/gst-rates/>
4. <https://cleartax.in/s/what-is-input-credit-and-how-to-claim-it>
5. <https://taxguru.in/goods-and-service-tax/measures>